

BASOTHO COMMUNITY ELDERS' VIEWS ON BOTHU/UBUNTU AS A MORAL CONCEPT

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ABSTRACT

This article explores Basotho community elders' views and understanding of the concept of Ubuntu. The article draws on the study funded by National Research Foundation (NRF) which was entitled, the 'Archaeology of Ubuntu'. The data for the study were collected through oral historical conversations with community elders in Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia and Swain, the District of Berea in Lesotho. The article is premised on the assumption that Botho/Ubuntu presupposes humaneness. In this article the notion of Ubuntu is taken to encapsulate moral norms and virtues such as kindness, generosity, compassion, benevolence, courtesy and respect and concern for others. Qualitative data show that Basotho community elders' understanding of Botho/Ubuntu resonates with the above-mentioned values. The Archaeology of Ubuntu study recognised community elders as custodians of indigenous African epistemologies. Basotho community elders linked Botho/Ubuntu with 'good conduct', 'good manners' and 'respect for others'. In this regard, therefore, the Basotho people tended to socialise the young people in respectful dispositions and humility.

Keywords: Archaeology of *Ubuntu*, *Botho/Ubuntu*, humanness, Basotho Community elders, oral tradition.

INTRODUCTION

The notion of *Botho/Ubuntu* has been widely theorised by African philosophers, scholars and researchers. *Botho/Ubuntu* has been portrayed as a 'moral theory' or 'a theory of right action' (Waghid, 2014; Letseka, 2000; Metz and Gaie, 2010; Metz, 2007; Teffo, 1994), as an ethic of care (Waghid and Smeyers, 2012), as a constitutional and jurisprudence principle (Mahao, 2010; Chaskalson, 2003; Mokgoro, 1998; Goldstone, 1997), and as a pedagogical principle (Letseka, 2013; Maharasoa and Maharasoa, 2004; Mapesela, 2004). The article, which is philosophical and speculative in nature, reports on the Basotho community elders' conceptions of the notion of *Ubuntu*. The study was made possible by funding from National Research Foundation (NRF) entitled 'Archaeology of *Ubuntu*'. The study was conducted in Botswana, Lesotho, Namibia, Swaziland, Zambia and Zimbabwe, and in the following provinces in South Africa, namely the Eastern Cape, Kwazulu-Natal, Limpopo, Mpumalanga and North West. The study recognised that community elders are custodians of indigenous African epistemologies (Keane, 2017; Hanisi, 2006; Maluleka, Wilkinson and Gumbo, 2006). As such, there was a need to engage them in oral historical conversations as the holders of Basotho forms of knowing. More so because every time an elder dies an important social, historical and cultural library disappears (Jewsiewicki and Mudimbe, 1993).

This article is divided into four sections. Firstly, we explore conceptions of *Botho/Ubuntu* as briefly sketched above. Secondly, we describe the study's research methodology, which is qualitative and entailed oral historical conversations with Basotho community elders. We were convinced that the community elders would provide information-rich transcriptions that would illuminate the questions to which we sought answers. We underscore the importance of communicating with community elders in their own language given that (a) language is considered a purveyor of a people's culture(s), while culture is the carrier of a people's "moral, aesthetic and ethical values" (Wa Thiong'o, 1993: 27). Wa Thiong'o (1993: 19) further reminds us that "the importance of the oral tradition is that through its agency African languages in their most magical form have been kept alive". Thirdly, we discuss the findings. We provide verbatim responses of community elders to questions on *Botho/Ubuntu*. Moreover, we show that Basotho community elders' understanding of the social and cultural import of *Botho/Ubuntu* are rigorous and coherent. This is consistent with Kenyan philosopher Oruka's (1990) views on Sage Philosophy. In the final section, we provide some concluding remarks.

THEORISING THE NOTION OF *BOTHO/UBUNTU*

The notion of *Botho/Ubuntu* has been variously delineated. In the 'Archaeology of *Ubuntu*' study from which this article draws, the notion of *Ubuntu* was conceptualised as humaneness; as a form of personhood; a normative concept or moral theory; as a potential pedagogical principle (Letseka, 2013, 2000), and as a notion of African communal justice or African jurisprudence (Mahao, 2010). Waghid and Davids (2014) argue that the notion of *Botho* or *Ubuntu* is constitutive of African political, social and ethical thought, often illuminating the communal interdependence of persons geared towards the cultivation of human flourishing in indigenous African societies. Letseka (2000: 185) contends that "*Botho* or *Ubuntu* should be understood to mean humaneness". The dictionary meaning of humaneness is that which is "characterized by kindness, mercy or compassion", or "characterized by an emphasis on humanistic values and concerns". In contrast, Mokgoro (1998: 16) posits that *Ubuntu* "is a humanistic orientation towards fellow beings". She argues that its value is viewed as "its basis for a morality of cooperation, compassion, communalism, concern for the interest of the collective respect, and respect for the dignity of personhood, with emphasis on the virtue of that dignity in social relationships and practice" (Mokgoro, 1998: 17).

For Ramose (2003: 382), "the logic of *Ubuntu* is towardsness". *Ubuntu* is associated with the adage, *umuntu ngumuntu ngabantu* (Nguni), or its Sesotho variation, *motho ke motho ka batho*, whose English translation approximates "a person is a person through other persons". Furthermore, Metz and Gaie (2010: 275) argue that *Umuntu ngumuntu ngabantu* indicates some descriptive claims about the dependence of a human being, particularly a child, on other human beings for her survival or for the course her life takes. Metz (2007: 323) posits that "*Ubuntu/Botho* grounds a normative ethical theory of right action, analytically

setting aside *Ubuntu/Botho* as a comprehensive worldview or a description of a way of life as a whole". It is his contention that the most justified normative theory of right action that has an African pedigree is the requirement to produce harmony and to reduce discord (Metz, 2007: 340).

Salzberg (2004: 5) argues that "kindness is compassion in action", and "the foundation of unselfconscious generosity, natural inclusivity and an unfeigned integrity". These views resonate with Sindane's (1994: 8) position that "to utter the phrase *umuntu ngumuntu ngabantu* inspires us to expose ourselves to others, to encounter the difference of their humanness so as to enrich our own". In the same vein, Louw's (2006: 167) stance that *Ubuntu* dictates that if we are to be human, we need to recognise the genuine otherness of our fellow citizens, and to acknowledge the diversity of our languages, histories, values and customs. The section that follows describes the study's research methodology.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The article is rooted in the discipline of African philosophy. Gyekye (1997) argues that philosophy is a conceptual response to basic human problems at different epochs. It speculates about a whole range of the human experiences. It provides conceptual speculation and analysis of the said human experiences. With respect to African philosophy, Letseka (2000: 179) argues that it should "speculate about and provide conceptual interpretation and analysis of human problems and human experience in the African context".

The data from which this article is based is derived from a qualitative study. In 2014 the study's research team conducted oral historical conversations (structured interviews) with Basotho community elders in the District of Berea, in Lesotho. The interviews for the Lesotho chapter of the article were conducted in Sesotho given the oral historical nature of the study. The following research questions guided the researchers in their conversations with community elders:

- What is your understanding of the notion of *Ubuntu*?
- How would you describe the way communities were organised?
- How would you describe the way communities educated the young people?
- How was the notion of justice understood with respect to different levels of intervention?

Historian, Jan Vansina (2006) reminds us that oral tradition forms the main available source for the construction of the past. Vansina (1985: 197) argues that "the genres of oral tradition in oral societies are as diverse as those of documents in a literate one. Their contents range over all aspects of human activity from demographic data to various sorts of data about art. Their range is wider than that of documents in most literate societies and includes the evidence which oral history there unearths". Henige (1982: 20) contends that "strictly speaking, oral traditions are those recollections of the past that are commonly or universally known in a given culture. Versions that are not widely known should rightfully

be considered a ‘testimony’ and if they relate to recent events they belong to the realm of oral history”.

Jewsiewicki and Mudimbe (1993) contend that "oral historiographies have always been bearers of norms and of logical systems for the interpretation of the past". It is their view that the "sense of the past creates a line between the past, the present and the future of Africa". Egan (1992: 641) notes that "oral cultures place significant emphasis on memory to preserve knowledge, lore and customs". Similarly, Mandela (1995: 24) recalls that in his native Thembuland in the former Transkei the elders (or the *izikhulu*) "were wise men who retained the knowledge of tribal history and custom in their heads and whose opinions carried great weight".

The ‘Archaeology of *Ubuntu*’ study’s conversations with Basotho community elders were conducted in December 2014. Seven elders aged between 68 and 95 years with whom agreements were signed were consulted (Table 1).

Table 1: Community elders (participants), by gender and age.

Participants	Male	Female	Age
Participant 1	X		95
Participant 2	X		80
Participant 3	X		88
Participant 4	X		75
Participant 5	X		68
Participant 6		X	88
Participant 7		X	75

The selection of elders was purposive. Purposive sampling is defined as “a form of non-probability sampling in which decisions concerning the individuals to be included in the sample are taken by the researcher, based upon a variety of criteria which may include specialist knowledge of the research issue, or capacity and willingness to participate in the research” (Oliver, 2006: 244). Saumure and Given (2008: 562) argue that “purposive sampling refers to a process where participants are selected because they meet criteria that have been predetermined by the researcher as relevant to addressing the research question (e.g. people of a particular age or other demographic category)”. Similarly, Creswell (2009: 217) opines that “purposeful sampling is used so that individuals are selected because they have experienced the central phenomenon”. The logic and power of purposive sampling “lies in selecting information-rich cases whose study will illuminate the question under study” (Patton, 2002: 230).

Each research was allocated ten community elders who would serve as the study’s respondents. Given the advanced age and frailty of some of the elders, the conversations were planned as courtesy visits that had to be courteous and gentle with the community elders. The research team was accompanied by a family elder who was acquainted with the community as neighbours. The

conversations started with informal introductions and reminisced among the elders. For instance, Participant 1 (aged 95 years), who was a peer of one of the researchers' fathers recalled their herd boy's days in the 1940s:

"Ntatao (Ramosese) ene e le motjodi oa sebele".
 ("Your father (Ramosese) was an exemplary herd boy".)

The conversations were guided by the 'interview tool', which demarcated four key themes as follows:

Ubuntu as a worldview and normative principle;
Ubuntu as a notion of African social justice;
Ubuntu as public policy; and
Ubuntu as a pedagogical principle.

The conversations were audio-taped. Brod, Tesler and Christensen (2009) argue that to document transparency, and for purposes of analysis and review of data, all interviews should be recorded and transcribed. Kidd and Parshall (2000: 298) posit that "audiotape is often easier for a transcriptionist to work with than videotape." Crucially, qualitative researchers agree that audiotaping is necessary in order for researchers to "remedy common, everyday memory problems" (Vemuri, Schmandt, Bender, Tellex and Lasse, 2004). Drawing on Daniel Schacter's (1999) seminal work, "The Seven Sins of Memory: Insights from Psychology and Cognitive Neuroscience", Vemuri *et al.* (2004) argue that some of the key features of the 'seven sins' can be attributed to the corruption of data derived from structured interviews (Table 2). They point out that under the category, 'forgetting' interviewees' memory tends to fade over time. Interviewees tend to be absent-minded during the interview, or block answers to questions they are uncomfortable with. While under the category, 'distortion' interviewees might have the right memory, but reply using the wrong source(s) of information and can be biased in their responses. Vemuri *et al.* (2004) argue that an audio-based information-retrieval tool can serve as a memory aid for blocking and transience memory problems.

Table 2: Six of the seven 'Sins of Memory'.

Forgetting	Distortion
Transience (memory fading over time)	Misattribution (right memory, wrong source)
Absent-mindedness (shallow processing, forgetting to do things)	Suggestibility (implanting memories, leading questions)
Blocking (memories temporarily unavailable)	Bias (distortions and unconscious influences)

Source: Vemuri *et al.* (2004): An Audio-Based Personal Memory Aid.

In another publication Schacter, Chiao and Mitchell (2003: 227) argue that the seven sins describe those ways in which the normal, everyday operations of our minds may occasionally produce suboptimal or flawed memory experiences. We recognise that in, and by themselves, structured interviews or conversations

might not always yield valid and dependable data from which researchers can make inferences. In the 1950s, Dean and Whyte (1958) asked a critical question: “How do you know if the informant is telling the truth?” They noted that “those who ask the question seem bothered by the insight that people sometimes say things for public consumption that they would not say in private. And sometimes they behave in ways that seem to contradict or cast serious doubt on what they profess in open conversation. So, the problem arises: “Can you tell what a person really believes on the basis of a few questions put to him in an interview?” (Dean and Whyte, 1958: 34). Dean and Whyte cautioned that “the informant’s statement represents merely the perception of the informant, filtered and modified by his cognitive and emotional reactions and reported through his personal verbal usages”. Concomitantly, Lunt (1996: 80) cautions that the decisions and rationale behind the use of interviews “often remain implicit with the research presenting the findings as if no choices had been made beyond that of using focus groups in the first place”.

The conduct of research in the ‘Archaeology of *Ubuntu*’ study was guided by the research ethical codes and principles as stated in the UNISA (2013) Policy on Research Ethics. These include the notion of informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, non-disclosure of participants’ identities and a commitment to a just and fair treatment of research participants at all times. During the Lesotho leg of the study the lead researcher, speaking in the local language, Sesotho, provided the research participants with a full disclosure of the policy’s ethical requirements as follows:

“Mokhoa oo re sebetsang ka ona ha re etsa lipatlisong tse tsoanang le ena ea Botho, re eletsa babuisane ba rona hore ba bua le rona ka khetho ea bona. Ka nako efe kapa efe, ha u ikutloa u so sa batle ho buoa le rona, u na le tokelo ea ho re bolella hore hau sa batla ho buoa, kape hau battle ho araba potso e eitseng haeba u sa ikutloe hantle”.

(“The procedure when we conduct interviews such as this one on *Botho/Ubuntu*, is that we should advise our participants that they talk to us voluntarily. At any time when you don’t want to continue with this conversation, you have a right to let us know, or that you are uncomfortable with a particular question, and you shall therefore not answer it”.)

PRESENTATION OF FINDINGS

The section presents the findings of the study. Information gleaned from the conversations with Basotho community elders suggested that ‘good moral behaviour’ was attributed to the inculcation of *Botho* or *Ubuntu*. For instance, when asked about his view of *Botho* or *Ubuntu*, Participant 1 (male aged 95 years) responded as follows:

“Motho ha a na le botho ene ele hobane a etsa lintho tse ntle, a sa phele ka lintho tse mpe tse re ka li nahanang kapa tseo ngoana a ka li etsang kapa motho a ka li etsang. U ne a etsa lintho tse ntle tseo u ka li supang hore u

holisitsoe joalo, u rutuoe joalo, u lauoe joalo. Joale a lula a li etsa ntho tseno tse ntle le mahlong a batho. Joale ke tsona ntho tseo ho tla thoe ... a hlompha. Ke tsona ntho tseo ke nahanang hore ke tsona botho. Ha ho thoe "motho o na le botho" ke hobane a phethahetse a etsa ntho tse ntle tse a amohelehang mahlong a batho."

("The character quality of *Botho* or *Ubuntu* suggests that a person does good things instead of the opposite we expect a child, or another person can do. Good conduct was indicative of how a person was raised, taught and instructed. Therefore, they would always be perceived in good light by members of society, e.g. commended for being respectful. These, I think, were indicators of *Botho* or *Ubuntu* in a person. People who possess the quality of *Botho* or *Ubuntu* conduct themselves in the manner perceived by others as good or acceptable".)

When the same question was put to Participant 3 (male aged 88 years), he too referred to the importance of role modelling in the family:

"Ha ho ne ho thoe motho ha ana botho ho ne ho supjoa linthonyana tse maloa empa haholo e ne ele mokhoa oo motho eo a phelang ka oona, bophelo ba hae. O na lebeletsoe hore a etse lintho tse khahlang batho ba bangata hobane ho ne ho tsejoa hore ha se batho bohle ba ka khahloang ke litsela tsa motho tsa ho phela."

("When you said a person has *Botho* or *Ubuntu*, a number of things came to mind. Firstly, it would be the way a person led or conducted their life. Such a person was expected to do good and praiseworthy things in the opinion of most people because it is in any case impossible to please everybody".)

Participant 3 noted that:

"Joale ha ho ne ho thoe ngoana enoa ha ana botho, ho ne ho shebiloe mekhoha ea ho etsa lintho. Mohlomong ele ngoana ea boitsoaro bo seng botle ha ho thoe ha ana mekhoha. Empa ngoana eo ha batho bohle ba mo talima, ba bile ba sebetsa le eena, baneng ba khahloa ke bophelo ba hae kapa ke lintho tseo a li etsang, ba ne ba re ngoana enoa o mekhoha e metle, ho bonahala hore o tsoa lelapeng le phelang."

("When it was noted that a child was devoid of *Botho* or *Ubuntu*, it would be related to how such a child conducted themselves in society. Perhaps it would be a child whose behaviour was so bad would be regarded as an affront to *Botho* or *Ubuntu*. On the other hand, a child who was admired by most people because of his or her good conduct was said to have good manners that were probably attributed to good parenthood".)

Mapesela (2004: 322) notes that "the indigenous Basotho communities ensured their continued survival and avoided the many social hardships such as disease, famine and crime. They inculcated good ethics, morals and values, such as humaneness (*Ubuntu*), neighbourliness, responsibility and respect for self and others." Seema (2012: 133) argues that "*hlompho* means to show respect to

have respect for one's parent or an elderly person, but especially for women in particular." Rudwick (2008: 155) posits that *hlompho* "resonates with customary rules that govern relationships at different levels of society in that it entails conventions regulating and controlling posture, gesture, dress code and other behavioural patterns".

Asked how the Basotho children were socialised or initiated into disciplined dispositions, Participant 4 noted that:

"Ngoana oa Mosotho o ne a hlompha... eseng feela uena ea neng a mo khalemela empa o ne a hlompha batsoali ba hae hobane tsoaro eo motho ea ne a ileng a o tsoara ka eona, batsoali ba hao ba ne ba tla tla o tsoara ka eona. Me ba be ba lumelle motho ea ne hore o nepile. Joale ke nthoena malapa a neng a tseba ho khalemela bana, bana ba teng ba ne ba tsebahala ka tsela eno."

(“A Mosotho child was respectful to all adults and not just his or her parents. They knew that the way any adult would discipline them, was the same their parents would also discipline them. It was therefore no use appealing to one's parents because they would also confirm that the adult who disciplines them was right to discipline them the way he or she did. This is why children were regarded as reflection of how well their families were raising them in terms of discipline”.)

One of the issues that emerged from the oral historical conversations is the moral role of stories and folktales (*ditšomo*) to the development of young people's dispositions of *Botho* or *Ubuntu*. Kock (1997: 355) notes that in Sesotho culture the *ditšomo* or *dipale* were a pre-Christian philosophy of life that articulated righteousness and empathy. For Coplan (1993: 92), the *ditšomo* serve as a form of school for the teaching of literature and history. Their aim is to expose a Mosotho child to “the principles and contradictions of social philosophy and social behaviour”. Ntsihlele (2003: 135) argues that “through the educational value of folktales (or *ditšomo*), virtues and vices were pointed out in those tales that had a specific didactic content”. Nussbaum (1997: 89) contends that storytelling enables children to acquire “essential moral capacities”. Through listening to stories children “learn to attribute life, emotion and thought to a form whose insides are hidden”. Therefore, storytelling is moral in the sense that it tells not only what happened, but also what ought to have happened. Responding to the question on the moral importance of *ditšomo* among the Basotho, Participant 7 (female aged 75 years) noted that:

"U no ka fetisa molaetsa ho bana ka ho ba ruta tšomo e nang le moelelo oa bohlokoa, 'me ha e felile ba ne ba utlousisa. Litšomo ene e le tsela ea ho fetisetsa ho bana thuto ea hore ba qetelle ba utloisisa ntho eo u ba rutang eona ka setšoantšo seno se u ntseng u ba joetsa sona batla utloa hore e feela re tšoanetse ho etsa tjena. Mona motho enoa o n'a tšoanetse hore ebe o entse tjena. O nepile kapa haa nepa".

(“You could convey an important message through *tšomo*/folktale to teach children something important, and at the end they would understand. Indeed, *tšomo*/folktales were useful educational tools because they had meaningful lessons and experiences such that if children understood them. They would then take up the lesson of what to do and not to do. The same can be said of proverbs. These traditions were educational and had illustrative power to communicate precise lessons and codes of conduct”.)

CONCLUSION

The article reported on the Basotho community elders' conceptions of the notion of *Botho/Ubuntu*. It proposed a view of *Ubuntu* as humaneness. It showed that the Basotho community elders' conceptions of the social and cultural import of *Botho/Ubuntu* are rigorous, dialectical and deeply philosophical. The article drew on verbatim responses from the qualitative data emphasise that Basotho the community elders associated *Botho/Ubuntu* with 'good conduct', possession of 'good manners', and being 'respectful of others'. Respect, or *hlompho*, which is also a critical *Ubuntu* value was presented as a conduct that recognises customary rules that govern human relationships and behavioural patterns at different levels of society. What became evident from the engagements with Basotho community elders is that Basotho communities invest heavily in the initiation of the young people in dispositions for *Ubuntu* moral values and principles.

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